

Ethnomedicine for Gastric Disorders Used by the Tribals of Khammam District, Andhra Pradesh, India

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Abstract- This paper deals with 58 species of plants covering 55 genera and 38 families used by the tribes of Khammam district, Andhra Pradesh, for the treatment of gastric disorders. Fabaceae is represented by a maximum of 4 species. Herbs are dominant with 22 species. Morphological analysis showed the maximum utilization of roots in 12 practices followed by leaf (11) and others. Forty practices are found to be new.

Keywords: Constipation, Digestive disorders, Flatulence, Gastritis, Indigestion, Ulcers

I. INTRODUCTION

Gastrointestinal (GI) diseases are a group of conditions that affect the digestive tract, including the esophagus, stomach, intestines, rectum and anus. They can be benign or malignant and are generally categorized as either functional or structural. Functional GIDs occur when the digestive tract does not function properly, but the structure appears normal. Structural GIDs are caused by physical abnormalities in the digestive organs. Structural Gastrointestinal diseases are typically more complicated. They tend to cause symptoms that last longer and do not get better with lifestyle changes alone. E.g., Hemorrhoids, colon polyps and inflammatory bowel disease. Some of the most common GI conditions are constipation, IBS, hemorrhoids, colitis, diarrhea, stomach pain, gastritis, gastroenteritis, indigestion (dyspepsia),

Khammam district is surrounded by Chhattisgarh and Odisha states in the North, Krishna district in the South, East and West Godavari districts in the East and Nalgonda and Warangal districts in the West. The geographical coordinates of the district falls within the longitudes of 79°47' and 81°47' E and the latitudes of 16°45' and 18°35' N occupying an area of 16, 029 sq km with a total forest area of 7, 594.38 sq km. The tribal population of India is 8.2% and Andhra Pradesh has 7.0% tribal population. Khammam district with 26.47% tribal population stands first in the state (Census 2011) and is the home of six tribal communities, viz., Koya, Lambada, Gond/Naikpod, Yerukula, Nayak and Konda Reddi. No prior studies have documented gastric disorders among the tribes of Khammam district, Andhra Pradesh, leading to the present investigation. Papers on hemorrhoids (Manjula et al. 2013), diarrhoea (Manjula and Reddi 2016) and stomach ache (Manjula and Reddi 2019) were already published.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Ethnobotanical survey was conducted in tribal rich habitations of Khammam district once in every two months from 2008 to 2012 with a duration of 10-15 days. About 4-7 days were spent during each trip with different tribal communities in their dwellings. After establishing good rapport with them, the utility of plants and detailed methods of uses were documented. In 102 pockets of the study area, 102 *vaidhyas* and practitioners were consulted. Data collected were cross checked with the data obtained from same as well as on different settlement on different occasions for authenticity. Voucher specimens were collected in both flowering and fruiting stages, herbarium specimens were prepared and deposited in the Herbarium of the Department of Botany, Andhra University, Visakhapatnam (AUV), after identification.

III. ENUMERATION

The plants are enumerated alphabetically with valid botanical name followed by family, vernacular name, English name, locality, collector and voucher number. Each ethno-medicinal practice is provided with the part(s) used, method of preparation, mode of administration, dosage and the tribal informant in parenthesis. Plants and practices marked with an asterisk (*) are considered to be new or less known.

Abelmoschus moschatus Medic. Malvaceae VN: Yerra benda E: Musk mallow Bethampudi, RRM 10038

***Gastric:** Equal quantities of fruit peel along with fruit pulp of albakara and tender leaves of *Syzygium cumini* are ground. Ten gm of that paste is administered with water once a day for 3 days (Koya).

Acacia caesia (L.) Willd. Fabaceae VN: Korintha E: African acacias
Chintur, RRM 10172

***Flatulence:** Ten ml of root paste is taken orally twice a day (Gond).

Acacia catechu (L. f.) Willd. Fabaceae VN: Sandra E: Cutch tree Bethampudi, RRM 10000

Mouth ulcers: Stem bark decoction is gargled once a day for 3 days (Konda Reddi).

Aegle marmelos (L.) Correa. Rutaceae VN: Maredu E: Bael tree Chintur, RRM 10165

Gastric trouble: Three spoonful of root decoction is administered daily once till cure (Yerukula).

Indigestion: Stem bark powder mixed with cow milk is administered in 2-3 spoonful once a day for 3-4 days (Koya).

Ailanthus excelsa Roxb. Simaroubaceae VN: Pedda maanu E: Tree of heaven Vajedu, RRM 10136

***Constipation:** One spoonful of stem bark powder mixed with one spoonful of jaggery is administered once a day for 2-3 days before going to bed (Gond).

Allium sativum L. Liliaceae VN: Tellagadda E: Garlic Gummadi Doddi, RRM 10137

Gastric trouble: Bulbs with leaves of *Andrographis paniculata* and *Coleus amboinicus* are taken in equal quantities and ground. Two spoonful of paste is administered daily once for 8 days (Lambada).

Alpinia galanga (L.) Willd. Zingiberaceae VN: Dumparastram E: Greater galangal Chiruthapalli, RRM 10034

***Indigestion:** Rhizome decoction mixed with one spoonful of *Carum copticum* is administered twice a day for 3 days (Konda Reddi).

Amaranthus spinosus L. Amaranthaceae VN: Mulluthotakoora E: Prickly amaranth Peruru, RRM 10168

Constipation: Thirty ml of whole plant decoction is taken once a day for 3 days (Gond).

Ampelocissus latifolia (Roxb.) Planch. Vitaceae VN: Adaviteega draksha E: Wild grape Yerram Padu, RRM 10063

***Ulcers:** Twenty ml of leaf decoction mixed with one spoonful of honey is administered twice a day till cure (Koya).

Andrographis paniculata (Burm. f.) Wall. ex Nees Acanthaceae VN: Nela veemu E: King of bitters Nagupalli, RRM 10110

***Ulcers:** Twenty ml of whole plant decoction mixed with one spoonful of crystal sugar is administered once a day for 5-7 days (Konda Reddi).

Argyrea nervosa (Burm. f.) Boj. Convolvulaceae VN: Samudrapala E: Elephant creeper Yetapaka, RRM 10107

***Constipation:** Roots are ground with six black pepper seeds and half spoon of it is taken orally for 4 days (Gond).

Averrhoa carambola L. Averrhoaceae VN: Zeera E: Carambola apple Edugurallapalli, RRM 10112

***Digestive disorders:** One spoonful of fruit powder is taken with honey or sugar syrup once a day till cure (Nayak).

Basella rubra L. Basellaceae VN: Yerra bachli E: Indian spinach Rabbavaram, RRM 10092

Gastric: Two spoonful of root decoction is administered daily once for till cure (Lambada).

Blumea mollis (D.Don) Merr. Asteraceae VN: Kukkapogaku E: Top blumea Rajeswarapuram, RRM 10174

***Ulcers in stomach:** Fifteen ml of whole plant decoction mixed with one cup of curd is administered twice a day till cure (Koya).

Boswellia serrata Roxb. ex Colebr. Burseraceae VN: Anduga E: Indian olibanum Lakshmipuram, RRM 10044

***Gastric:** Twenty ml of seed decoction is administered once a day for 5 days (Lambada).

Breynia retusa (Dennst.) Alston Euphorbiaceae VN: Chinna purugudu E: Cup saucer plant Gowridevipeta, RRM 10147

***Ulcers:** Ten ml of root decoction mixed with one spoonful of honey is taken twice a day for 5-7 days (Konda Reddi).

Capsicum annuum L. Solanaceae VN: Mirapa E: Chilli Pathalingala, RRM 10078

Indigestion: Equal quantities of seeds and root of *Acorus calamus* are roasted and mixed with water and filtered. One cup is administered once a day till cure (Lambada).

Carica papaya L. Caricaceae VN: Boppayi E: Papaya Thimmarapeta, RRM 10079

Gastric trouble: Latex is dried in sun light and made into powder. Half spoonful of powder is administered with water (Lambada).

Chloroxylon swietenia DC. Rutaceae VN: Billudu E: Satin wood tree Vissapuram. RRM 10156

***Indigestion:** Two spoonful of stem bark paste is administered twice a day for 2 days (Gond).

Coriandrum sativum L. Apiaceae VN: Dhaniyalu E: Coriander Yetapaka, RRM 10057

Indigestion: Three spoonful of seed paste mixed with half spoon of dried ginger powder is taken orally once a day for 3 days (Nayak).

Crataeva religiosa G. Forst. Capparaceae VN: Ulimiri E: Three leaved caper

Chinnanallabelli, RRM 10130

***Intestinal ulcers:** Three spoonful of leaf juice is taken twice a day for 7 days (Koya).

Cuminum cyminum L. Apiaceae VN: Jeelakarra E: Cumin Lakshmipuram, RRM 10327

Indigestion: Two spoonful of seed powder mixed with one glass of water is taken once a day for 2 days (Lambada).

Curcuma aromatica Salisb. Zingiberaceae VN: Kasthuri dumpa, E: Wild turmeric Peruru, RRM 10226

***Digestive disorders and *Gastric disorders:** Fifteen ml of whole plant decoction is taken twice a day for 15 days (Gond).

Cuscuta reflexa Roxb. Cuscutaceae VN: Pachiteega E: Horse tail parasite

Gummadi Doddi, RRM 10328

***Gastrics and Indigestion:** Three spoonful of whole plant decoction mixed with one spoonful of crystal sugar is administered once a day for 5 days early in the morning (Konda Reddi).

Cynodon dactylon (L.) Pers. Poaceae VN: Garika gaddi E: Bahama grass

Gondigudem, RRM 10321

Ulcers: Half cup of tuber decoction is administered twice a day for 5-7 days (Koya).

Euphorbia heterophylla L. Euphorbiaceae VN: Osso E: Marieclaire

Edugurallapalli, RRM 10291

***Colic:** Thirty ml of whole plant decoction is taken twice a day for 45 days (Gond).

Ficus hispida L. Moraceae VN: Brahma medi E: Wild fig Chiruthapalli, RRM 10331

***Colic in children:** Fine cloth dipped in latex is plastered around the stomach (Konda Reddi).

Ficus racemosa L. Moraceae VN: Medi E: Gular fig Dummugudem, RRM 10365

***Colic in children:** Latex is applied on the forehead and navel till cure (Nayak).

Ficus virens Aiton Moraceae VN: Banda juvvi E: Maiden hair tree Soraveedu, RRM 10243

Ulcers: Thirty ml of stem bark decoction mixed with one spoonful of honey is administered once a day till cure (Koya).

Firmiana simplex (L.) W. Wight Sterculiaceae VN: Kondagogu E: Gum karaya Bhadrachalam, RRM 10431

***Constipation:** Five g of young root paste is taken orally once a day till cure (Gond).

Hibiscus fuscus Garcke . Malvaceae VN: Konda gongura E: Shoe flower Gundala, RRM 10354

***Indigestion:** Twenty ml of leaf decoction mixed with honey is taken twice a day till cure (Konda Reddi).

Ipomoea nil (L.) Roth Convolvulaceae VN: Kala dana E: Morning glory

Edugurallapalli, RRM 10200

Constipation: Seed powder mixed with dried ginger and sugar are taken in equal quantities and made into soap nut seed size pills and one pill is administered with lukewarm water once a day for 3 days (Gond).

Leucas aspera (Willd.) Link. Lamiaceae VN: Tummi E: Thumbbe Ellendu, RRM 10277

Mouth ulcers: Leaf decoction is gargled once a day till cure (Nayak).

Limonia acidissima Groff. Rutaceae VN: Velakkaya E: Elephant apple Sarapaka, RRM 10415

***Stomach disorder:** Three spoonful of fruit pulp is administered once a day for 3 days or fruit pulp is taken once a day till cure (Lambada).

Lycopersicon esculentum Mill. Solanaceae VN: Thakkali E: Tomato Thaliperu, RRM 10275

***Constipation:** Thirty ml of fruit juice is taken once a day till cure (Gond).

***Indigestion:** Flowers fried and made into powder is administered in 2 spoonful along with a cup of water once a day for 3 days (Koya).

Mangifera indica L. Anacardiaceae VN: Mamidi chettu E: Mango Gummadi Doddi, RRM 10377

Abdominal pain: Stem bark decoction is administered twice a day till cure (Nayak).

Mentha spicata L. Lamiaceae VN: Pudhina E: Spearmint Lakshmiapuram, RRM 10238

Gastric disorders: Leaf decoction is administered in 50 ml dose once daily (Lambada).

Morinda pubescens Smith Rubiaceae VN: Maddi chettu E: Indian mulberry Gopalapuram, RRM 10097

***Digestive disorders:** Thirty ml of fruit juice is taken once a day till cure (Koya).

Moringa oleifera Lamk. Moringaceae VN: Karumunaga E: Drumstick tree Vajedu, RRM 10307

Indigestion in children: One spoonful of stem bark decoction mixed with a pinch of salt is administered once a day till cure (Yerukula).

Mucuna pruriens (L.) DC. Fabaceae VN: Duladundi E: Cowitch Chikupalli, RRM 10306

Indigestion: Ten ml of leaf juice is administered twice a day till cure (Gond).

Musa paradisiaca L. Musaceae VN: Arati E: Plantain Peruru, RRM 10372

Gastric: Flower juice is taken daily in doses of one spoonful once a day till cure (Konda Reddi).

Opuntia dillenii Haw. Cactaceae VN: Naga jamudu E: Prickly pear Peruru, RRM 10295

***Gastric:** Twenty ml of root juice is taken along with half spoon of black pepper powder twice a day for 3 days (Yerukula).

***Mouth ulcers:** Fruits are eaten once a day till cure (Gond).

Phyllanthus acidus (L.) Skeels Euphorbiaceae VN: Rasa usiri E: Country gooseberry Peruru, RRM 10401

***Gastric:** Thirty gm of fruit pulp mixed with one spoonful of honey is administered twice a day till cure (Lambada).

Pimpinella tirupatiensis Bal. & Sub. Apiaceae VN: Adavi kothimera E: Forest coriander Yetapaka, RRM 10426

***Indigestion:** Ten ml of leaf juice is taken twice a day for 5 days (Gond).

Plectranthus barbatus Andrews Lamiaceae VN: Daggi aku E: Coleus Peruru, RRM 10190

***Indigestion:** Twenty ml of leaf juice is administered with one spoonful of honey twice a day for 3-5 days (Koya).

Plumbago zeylanica L. Plumbaginaceae VN: Tella chitramulam E: Ceylon leads wort Thaliperu, RRM 10445

***Gastric trouble:** One spoonful of stem bark powder is taken with water once a day till cure (Gond).

Roots are ground along with cumin seeds, asafoetida, dried ginger and soapnut and made into tablets of soapnut seed size and one tablet is administered before lunch once a day till cure (Konda Reddi).

Portulaca quadrifida L. Portulacaceae VN: Pavila kura E: Chicken weed Charla, RRM 10425

***Ulcers:** Thirty ml of whole plant juice is taken twice a day till cure (Nayak).

Punica granatum L. Punicaceae VN: Dhanimma E: Pomegranate Charla, RRM 10451

Gastric and *Ulcers: Fruit coat pestled with stem bark of *Alstonia scholaris* is administered in doses of 5 gm tablets once a day for one month (Lambada).

Rauvolfia tetraphylla L. Apocynaceae VN: Papataku E: Wild snake root Chikupalli, RRM 10433

***Ulcers:** Root powder mixed with a cup of water is administered once a day till cure (Nayak).

Rotheca serrata (L.) Steane & Mabb. Verbenaceae VN: Bommalamarri E: Beetle killer Gummadi Doddi, RRM 10159

***Intestinal ulcers:** Two spoonful of root powder mixed with one spoonful of sugar is administered twice a day for 7-9 days (Gond).

Saccharum officinarum L. Poaceae VN: Cheruku E: Sugarcane Tekulapalem, RRM 10448

***Ulcers:** Jaggery mixed with dried ginger powder is made into paste and 10 gm of it is taken twice a day for 40 days (Lambada).

Schleichera oleosa (Lour.) Merr. Sapindaceae VN: Buchi manu E: Lac tree Marlapadu, RRM 10450

***Gastric trouble:** Two spoonful of stem bark decoction mixed with one spoonful of fruit powders of *Terminalia chebula*, *T. bellerica* and *Phyllanthus emblica* is administered twice a day for 5-10 days (Koya).

Senna auriculata (L.) Roxb. Fabaceae VN: Tangedu E: Tanners cassia Peruru, RRM 10122

Constipation: Two spoonful of stem decoction is taken with a cup of water once a day for 3 days (Konda Reddi).

Stachytarpheta jamaicensis (L.) Vahl Verbenaceae VN: Erra uttareneni E: Aaron's rod Thotalagondi, RRM 10521

Ulcers: Twenty ml of tender leaf juice mixed with a cup of water is taken twice a day till cure (Gond).

Terminalia chebula Retz. Combretaceae VN: Karakkaya E: Chebulic myrobalan Lankapalli, RRM 10503

***Constipation:** Fifteen ml of root juice is administered daily once till cure (Yerukula).

Thysanolaena latifolia (Roxb. ex Hornem.) Honda Poaceae VN: Konda cheepurugaddi E: Broom grass Charla, RRM 10484

***Indigestion:** Two spoonful of root decoction is administered twice a day till cure (Koya).

Vanda spathulata (L.) Spreng. Orchidaceae VN: Nusti badanika E: Wild celery Subbledu, RRM 10483

***Gastric:** Twenty ml of leaf juice is taken twice a day for 10 days (Gond).

Ventilago denticulata Willd. Rhamnaceae VN: Yerrabeni theega E: Red creeper Madaram, RRM 10500

***Mouth ulcers:** Leaf decoction is gargled once a day for 3 days (Konda Reddi).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The paper deals with 58 species of plants covering 55 genera and 38 families used by the tribes of Khammam district, Andhra Pradesh, for gastrointestinal diseases, viz., abdominal pain, colic, constipation, digestive disorders, flatulence, gastric, gastric disorders, gastric trouble, indigestion, mouth ulcers, stomach disorder, ulcers, ulcers in stomach. Fabaceae is the dominant family with 4 species followed by Rutaceae, Lamiaceae, Apiaceae, Moraceae, Euphorbiaceae, Poaceae (3 spp. each); Malvaceae, Convolvulaceae, Solanaceae, Verbenaceae, Zingiberaceae (2 spp. each), and Capparaceae, Avertroaceae, Sterculiaceae, Anardiaceae, Portulacaceae, Sapindaceae, Combretaceae, Rhamnaceae, Moringaceae, Simaroubaceae, Vitaceae, Burseraceae, Basellaceae, Asteraceae, Rubiaceae, Apocynaceae, Cuscutaceae, Acanthaceae, Caricaceae, Cactaceae, Plumbaginaceae, Punicaceae, Amaranthaceae, Musaceae, Liliaceae, Orchidaceae with one species each. Habit-

wise analysis showed the dominance of herbs with 22 species followed by trees (20 spp.) and shrubs (16 spp.). Morphological analysis showed the maximum utilization of root in 12 practices followed by leaf (11), stem bark, fruit (8 each), whole plant (7), seed (5), latex (3), stem, flower (2 each) and bulb, rhizome, tuber in one practice each. They are administered either in the form of juice, paste, decoction, tablets, along with either water, honey, ginger powder, black pepper powder, crystal sugar, cow milk, jaggery, salt, sugar syrup, curd, Of the total 61 practices 40 were found to be new or less known (Jain, 1991; Kirtikar and Basu, 2003; Jain and Jain, 2016). Plants used for similar purpose in different parts of India are *Cuscuta reflexa* by the Yanadi, Nakkala, Iruka, Yerukala, Sugali/Lambadi and Chenchu tribes of Chittoor district, Andhra Pradesh (Vedavathy *et al.* 1997); *Terminalia chebula* by Savara, Jatapu, Gadaba, Kondadora, Samantha tribes of Vizianagaram district, Andhra Pradesh (Venkaiah, 1998), Bhil, Bhil-Meena, Damor, Dhanka, Garasia, Kathodi, Kokna, Kolidhor, Naikara, Patelia, Meena, Seharua tribes of Rajasthan (Sharma and Kumar, 2007), Mishing, Deuris, Sonowal-Kachari tribes of Lakhimpur district, Assam (Kalita and Bora, 2008), Apatami, Mongpa, Singpho, Tanga, Padam, Ngishi, I-Idu tribes of Arunachal Pradesh (Khongsai *et al.* 2011); *Aegle marmelos* by Shabar, Saora, Kolha, Munda, Kandha, Santal, Ho, Bhumij, Lodha tribes of Jajpur district, Orissa (Satapathy and Brahmam, 1999), people in 10 southern and one northern districts of Karnataka (Shiddamallayya *et al.*, 2010) and *Ailanthus excelsa*, *Boswellia serrata* by Gond, Bheel, Kol, Auranb, Sahariya tribes of Gwalior Forest Division of Madhya Pradesh (Anis *et al.* 2000). On studying the plants as sources of medicines, it has been felt that a thorough pharmacognostic and a scientific evaluation of these plants have become very important as the tribals have used these plants since time immemorial and their uses established as any other medicines. The information on folk medicines has to be further studied and tested. They should not be taken as the only and final way of healing.

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